

Register of RLA Scenarios for Duplicate and/or Private Records in the Digital Science Data Hub

Document purpose: Following a meeting on Friday 11 October 2024, this document can be used to record scenarios for possible privacy and duplication issues when combining data from different universities in the RLA Data Hub (Digital Science)

Final state 1 November 2024

Ready to provide to Tech meeting? Decision: YES

Future plan: Recommendation to Tech meeting. Once data is in RLA, look at workshops with University Data Providers

Reporter	Scenario - record as much as poss	Likelihood	Impact	Who resolves?	Possible processes, rules	Implement?
Jo D	Multiple versions of a grant: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Each with researchers from one university (the data provider) 	High ▾	Medium ▾	Within project team	OK if grant identifier is "identical" Duplicate identification within DS is likely to help Frequently (Currently) cannot tell if they are duplicate - not poss if insufficient info How identical do they have to be (eg ARC)	Data Hub ▾ If matchable Decision: Can be resolved in Data Hub Admin org rules

						Exception Report to both universities
Jo D	Multiple versions of a grant: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Each with different levels of privacy 	Low ▾	High ▾		Defer. Action: Seeking frequency info. Cannot automate Funder rule - Admin org? Admin org rules Advise provider	Provider ▾ Decision: Exception report to both universities
Jo D	Multiple versions of a grant: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Each with different FORs, SEOs etc added 	High ▾	Low ▾	Could be automated	Add as needed (Chun) Up to 3 Could be used to train an RLA LLM. Lyle proposed: Should we provide an exceptions report to providers. Either rely on the related providers to troubleshoot, or perhaps ARDC holds a regular Uni-providers meetings to discuss exceptions report. (suggestion related to multiple scenarios) Admin org version of the truth rules - keep additional in RLA	Data Hub ▾ If matchable Decision: Can be resolved in Data Hub Admin org rules Keep additional codes in RLA
Jason S	For SCU funder name is de-identified (excluding ARC, MRFF and NHMRC) which could be an issue with de-duplication if that is based on funder name	High ▾	Medium ▾		OK if the title can be matched in DS, and other info eg chief investigators, is available Lyle: De-duplication with another Uni, I'm not worried about that, but we've been told "repeat business" within a Uni/researcher is crucial. Can SCU consider how we might	Data Hub ▾ If matchable... Decision: Can be resolved in Data Hub Admin org rules

					do that? Can we de-identify using just an identifier instead of the a funder name? Not possible if funder is a random number (GU) Project ID might be unique Might need to confirm	Exception Report to both universities
Jo D	A researcher leaves one uni and joins another - former uni does not update data so duplicate researchers on a grant	High ▾	Low ▾	Within project	Consider ORCID to resolve. Exception report	Provider ▾ Decision: Exception report to both universities
Jo D	2 unis on a grant. One no longer wants to be associated (researcher leaves)	High ▾	Low ▾	Within project	Info is not deleted. User is inactive for a university	Data Hub ▾ If matchable Decision: Can be resolved in Data Hub Admin org rules Exception Report to both universities
Isaac	Multi role researchers e.g. adjunct as GU/SCU/UTS whilst holding another research role at GU/SCU/UTS.	High ▾	Low ▾	Within project	Consider researcher's primary affiliation to be the default Admin organisation identification could be important Should be automatable. Ok to have duplicate researchers in this case Need to confirm	No ▾ Decision: No action in DS Data Hub

Isaac	Inconsistent taxonomies/terms of labeling. GU/SCU/UTS might call one type of research activity X, while another calls the same activity Y. Kind of related to Jo's point at row one. Essentially two records appear distinct but are indeed the same. A human might be able to identify that they are related but fuzzy matching logic might not be able to solve this sort of edge case.	High ▾	Medium ▾	Within project	<p>Need a mapping table Admin org probably calls the shots.</p> <p>Getting to the mapping table is the task.</p> <p>Lyle: Question to the Uni partners: should ARDC facilitate a working group on this post-project?</p>	<p>Data Hub ▾</p> <p>If matchable Decision: Can be resolved in Data Hub Admin org rules</p> <p>Exception Report to both universities</p>
Jo D	Two unis on a grant. One requests a take down.	Low ▾	High ▾	Within project	<p>Dependencies Info is available elsewhere Available on staff profile Republished everywhere Context-dependent Was it originally open?</p> <p>Admin org decision rules. Inform the org requesting the takedown</p>	<p>Provider ▾</p> <p>Decision: Exception report to both universities</p>
Jo D	University wants information to be private but the funder has published full information on their website	Me... ▾	Low ▾	Within project	<p>Likely to be easy Override of uni rules Issue in RLA ARDC platform, not DS Data Hub</p> <p>If matchable RLA will need to consider issuing exception report</p>	<p>Provider ▾</p> <p>Decision: No action in DS Data Hub</p> <p>Action can be taken in RLA Platform</p>
Jo D	University wants information to be private but researcher has published information on their ORCID profile	Me... ▾		Within project	<p>Not yet a problem.</p> <p>Will only showing in RLA ARDC Platform, not DS</p>	<p>Provider ▾</p> <p>Decision: No action in DS</p>

					<p>Lyle: Would the Unis like this info as part of an exceptions report from ARDC/RLA? The benefit might be making this visible, as it wasn't before. If matchable RLA will need to consider issuing exception report</p>	<p>Data Hub</p> <p>Action can be taken in RLA Platform</p>
Jo D	University originally requested information be private but since then the researchers have agreed to have their names published in a publication that acknowledges the grant	Low ▾	Low ▾		<p>Publications unlikely to emerge from contract research. If matchable RLA might need to consider issuing exception report</p>	<p>No ▾</p> <p>Decision: No action in DS Data Hub</p>